

Implications of Sustainable Development Goals and Covid 19

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Abstract

The agenda of implication of sustainable development goals is on the priority of every country. It is only the transformative vision for attainment of a better world for all. This is the agenda for pertaining to peace, prosperity, poverty eradication, and welfare of the humanity. It connotes an alarming stage for climate action, gender discrimination, inequality, injustice and devaluation of morals. It brings all the globe together with the instinct of leaving no one behind.

Keywords Sustainable Development, Covid 19, Climate Change, Gender Discrimination.

Introduction

The term sustainable development is widely used by everybody. The economic development concentrate on the growth of GDP till the decade of 80. If country claims a growth rate of 5% to 7%, connote a good development. The trickledown effect of this GDP growth affects all the sectors of the economy. During the decade of 80 economic development defined as REDISTRIBUTION WITH GROWTH. As DUDLEY SEERS asks three questions in regards of economic development –

1. Is there any decline in level of poverty?
2. Is there any decline in level of unemployment?
3. Is there any decline in the level of inequalities?

If the answers of all the three questions are positive, it is the evidence of economic growth, if any one of three indicators show negative result means there is no economic development reported. The whole world is progressing day by day. countries are using their resources without concerning their depletion. We can say that they are plundering the resources. All the resources used for the economic development are NON-RENEWABLE. According to the World development report 1992 there are two sides of the aspects of environmental degradation. one is Environment quality and another is Future productivity.

These are the circumstances leads the need of sustainable development.

Objective of study

The specific objectives of the proposed study are as-

1. To assess the role of sustainable development goals and MDGs.
2. To assess the after effects of COVID 19.
3. To find out implications of SDGs during COVID 19 breakout.

Review of Literature

The word sustainable development extensively used by political persons all over the world, but lack a consistent analysis. The concept is still being developed. And the definitions are regularly revised. The word was coined by Indian economist Nitin Desai, while he was a senior economic adviser to the world commission on environment and development (WCED). This was used very first time by the international union for the conservation of nature and natural resource while present the world conservation strategy. The commission published its report in Oct 1987, by united nations through Oxford university press, known as BRUNDTLAND report or Our Common Future. This

publication was in recognition of Gro Harlem Brundtland's, former Norwegian prime minister the chairperson of the WCED. This report recognized that human resources development in the form of poverty reduction, gender equity and wealth redistribution was crucial to formulating strategies for environmental conservation, and that environmental limits to economic growth in industrialized and industrializing societies. It develops the guiding principles for sustainable development and defined the sustainable development as

“Development which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generation to meet their own needs.”

I mean that **“if you are burning coal to produce electricity with that plant more trees to arrange coal for future generation”**

The four pillars of sustainable development are Economic, social, culture and environment.

Government must maintain the Environment Accounting System. Whenever there is a calculation of economic development and growth, there should be a cost and benefit analysis of natural resources.

Methodology

Data collected for the work through various secondary sources and day to day experiences.

In the year 2000 United Nations started work on the attainment of the sustainable development. In this regard leaders of 189 countries gathered at the United Nations headquarters and signed the historic Millennium declaration. Millennium development goals represents the commitments of united nations members states to reduce extreme poverty, hunger diseases, gender inequality, lack of education and access to basic infrastructure. They are eight in numbers all by target date by 2015, having 21 criteria.

Analysis

Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) 2000-2015

Goal I ensure the eradication of poverty with the target

1. To halve the proportion of people whose daily income is less than \$1.25
2. To achieve full and productive employment as well as decent work for all including young people and women.
3. To halve the proportion of individual suffering from hunger in the period between 1990 to 2015

Goal II ensures that children universally will be able to complete a full course of primary education by 2015.

Goal III ensures that eliminate gender disparity in primary and secondary education by 2005 and in all levels of education by 2015.

Goal IV ensures that reduce the under-five mortality rate by two -third in the period between 1990 and 2015, by improving food security and nutrition.

Goal V ensures that reduce the maternal mortality ratio by 75% and achieve universal access to reproductive health.

Goal VI ensures that

1. Achieve global access to treatment for HIV/AIDS for those who need it by 2010,
2. Halt by 2015 and reverse the spread of HIV/AIDS
3. Ceased and started reversal of the incidence of malaria and other major diseases by 2015.

Goal VII ensures that

1. Reverse the depletion of environment resources,
2. Reduce the biodiversity loss
3. Achieve a substantial reduction in the rate of loss by 2010,
4. Halve the proportion of the universal population without sustainable access to clean and safe drinking water and basic sanitation by 2015,
5. Achieve substantial improvement in the lives of a minimum of 100million slum dwellers by 2020.

Goal VIII ensures that

1. Develop an open predictable, rule based, nondiscriminatory trading economic system,
2. Address special needs of least developed countries, small island developing states and landlocked developing countries,
3. Deal with the debt problems of developing nations,
4. Provide access to affordable essential drugs in the developing world in collaborations with pharmaceutical companies.
5. Avail benefits of new technologies especially information and communication in collaboration with the private sector.

The MDGs helped to lift more than one billion people out of extreme poverty, enable more girls to attend school and change the trend on child mortality, maternal mortality, HIV/AIDS and tuberculosis. One of the major MDG failures is the fact that the success of the goals was not experienced equally across the globe.

Sustainable Development Goals: Due to failure of MDGs the concept of SDGs came in to existence. After that Global leader are regrouping and as the U.N Secretary General Ban Ki moon says **“The emerging post 2015development agenda, including the set of sustainable development goals, strives to build on our successes and put all countries together, firmly on track towards a more prosperous, sustainable and equitable world.**

Although there have been failures in trying to implement the goals, all hope is not lost. Progress in the form of Sustainable Development Goals expected. In the year 2015 Sustainable development goals were set up by United Nations General Assembly and are intended to be achieve by 2030. Sustainable development goals (SDGs) or Global Goals are a collection of 17 interlinked goals designed to be a “blue print to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all.” They are also known as Zero goals or Agenda 2030.The SDGs were developed in the post 2015 development agenda as the future global development framework to succeed the MDGs which were ended in2015. The latest data show that about one in eight people still lived in extreme poverty, nearly 800 million people suffered from hunger, the births of nearly a quarter of children under 5 had not been recorded, 1.1 billion people were living without electricity, and water scarcity affected more than 2 billion people. The Goals apply to all societies. Even the wealthiest countries have yet to fully empower women or eliminate discrimination. All nations will need to build the Sustainable Development Goals into their national policies and plans to achieve them.

Goal 1 calls for an end to poverty in all its manifestations, including extreme poverty, over the next 15 years. All people everywhere, including the poorest and most vulnerable, should enjoy a basic standard of living and social protection benefits.

Goal 2 seeks to end hunger and all forms of malnutrition and to achieve sustainable food production by 2030. It is premised on the idea that everyone should have access to sufficient nutritious food, which will require widespread promotion of sustainable agriculture, a doubling of agricultural productivity, increased investments and properly functioning food markets.

Goal 3 aims to ensure health and well-being for all at all ages by improving reproductive, maternal and child health; ending the epidemics of major communicable diseases; reducing non-communicable and environmental diseases; achieving universal health coverage; and ensuring access to safe, affordable and effective medicines and vaccines for all.

Goal 4 focuses on the acquisition of foundational and higher-order skills; greater and more equitable access to technical and vocational education and training and higher education; training throughout life; and the knowledge, skills and values needed to function well and contribute to society.

Goal 5 aims to empower women and girls to reach their full potential, which requires eliminating all forms of discrimination and violence against them, including harmful practices. It seeks to ensure that they have every opportunity for sexual and reproductive health and reproductive rights; receive due recognition for their unpaid work; have full access to productive resources; and enjoy equal participation with men in political, economic and public life.

Goal 6 goes beyond drinking water, sanitation and hygiene to also address the quality and sustainability of water resources. Achieving this Goal, which is critical to the survival of people and the planet, means expanding international cooperation and garnering the support of local communities in improving water and sanitation management.

Goal 7 seeks to promote broader energy access and increased use of renewable energy, including through enhanced international cooperation and expanded infrastructure and technology for clean energy.

Goal 8 aims to provide opportunities for full and productive employment and decent work for all while eradicating forced labour, human trafficking and child labour. can be accomplished through enhanced international and domestic financial, technological and technical support, research and innovation, and increased access to information and communication technology.

Goal 9 focuses on the promotion of infrastructure development, industrialization and innovation.

Goal 10 calls for reducing inequalities in income, as well as those based on sex, age, disability, race, class, ethnicity, religion and opportunity—both within and among countries. It also aims to ensure safe, orderly and regular migration and addresses issues related to representation of developing countries in global decision-making and development assistance.

Goal 11 aims to renew and plan cities and other human settlements in a way that fosters community cohesion and personal security while stimulating innovation and employment.

Goal 12 aims to promote sustainable consumption and production patterns through measures such as specific policies and international agreements on the management of materials that are toxic to the environment.

Goal 13 states that climate change presents the single biggest threat to development, and its widespread, unprecedented effects disproportionately burden the poorest and the most vulnerable. Urgent action is needed not only to combat climate change and its impacts, but also to build resilience in responding to climate-related hazards and natural disasters.

Goal 14 seeks to promote the conservation and sustainable use of marine and coastal ecosystems, prevent marine pollution and increase the economic benefits to small island developing States and LDCs from the sustainable use of marine resources

Goal 15 focuses on managing forests sustainably, restoring degraded lands and successfully combating desertification, reducing degraded natural habitats and ending biodiversity loss. All of these efforts in combination will help ensure that livelihoods are preserved for those that depend directly on forests and other ecosystems, that biodiversity will thrive, and that the benefits of these natural resources will be enjoyed for generations to come.

Goal 16 envisages peaceful and inclusive societies based on respect for human rights, the rule of law, good governance at all levels, and transparent, effective and accountable institutions. Many countries still face protracted violence and armed conflict, and far too many people are poorly supported by weak institutions and lack access to justice, information and other fundamental freedoms.

The 2030 Agenda requires a revitalized and enhanced global partnership that mobilizes all available resources from Governments, civil society, the private sector, the United Nations system and other actors. Increasing support to developing countries, in particular LDCs, landlocked developing countries and small island developing States is fundamental to equitable progress for all.

Conclusion

COVID 19 and Implications of SDGs

COVID 19 emerges as a pandemic affecting all over the world. Globe is suffering from this venomous virus. WHO declared the virus outbreak a pandemic in the second week of March 2020. During November last cases has been infection started in Wuhan after that, it spread drastically all over the world. Virulent disease emerges and spread quickly across the globe exposing the world to a whole new class of illness. Corona virus outbreak becomes a hindrance in world's economic growth. Every country in all continent is facing the ill effects of this pandemic. Due to non-availability of the vaccine and treatment of this disease, approx. all the countries apply lockdown as a precautionary measure to protect themselves become a victim of the epidemic. This results the lockdown of their Economies. All the supply chains are closed and demand chain also break. Indian economy is also facing the same for the economy. According to an estimate the growth rate of our economy become minus 2.1 during this phase. As all the economic activities during lockdown is close. We have five lockdowns gradually. In the last lockdown government has relax some sectors to revive our economy. Tourism sector, gym, cinema halls, Malls, Amusement parks, Hotel industry, real state sector, MSME, Transportation sector, restaurant, Health sectors, Saloons, parlors are badly affected. Government of India has announced a programme ATAMNIRBHR BHARAT for economic revival. It also released packages for boost up of Industry and for sake of all the people. To reach the benefit to the lowest level of the society was a tough task for the government. It will provide a credit facility to MSMEs and other industries. So, production will increase. It will infuse liquidity in the banking system of the country through various measures. It will provide direct cash transfers to the hands of migrant laborers. 11,120 crore have been approved. Out of this sanctioned amount, Rs 7,227 crore has been disbursed whereas Rs 182 crore will not be availed. The remaining sanctions of Rs 3,707 crore have lapsed. This Scheme has been closed on 30th September, 2020.

According to the report of Economic and Social council of united nations on implications of SDGs as the end of 2021 more than 5.4 million people worldwide had died directly due to COVID-19. Global health system disrupted. An additional 75 million to 95 million people will live in extreme poverty in 2022 compared to pre-pandemic level. Billions of children missed out on schooling and over 100 million more children fell down below the minimum reading proficiency level and other learnings especially in rural areas. Women and girls have also been affected by the socio-economic fallout of the pandemic, struggling with lost jobs, derailed education and domestic violence. During lockdown period environment degradation become less and level of pollution decreased. Climatic concern of SDG has positive effect. Economic slowdown led to the temporary reduction of CO2 emission in 2020. This crisis has also exacerbated all forms of malnutrition particularly in children. Between 2015 to 2020, the population using safely managed drinking water services increased from 70% to 74%. Lock down leads the water bodies having good quality. This pandemic caused the worst economic crisis in decades 2020. Severely damaging working time and income, rising inflation, supply-chain disruptions and unsustainable debt leads the economy to slow down. The world's ocean and seas continue struggle against increased acidification and plastic pollution. The pandemic increased the burden of single use plastic primarily from medical waste. Due to lockdown, there was a significant decline in fish production. This pandemic also led to reduction in tourism, causing substantial income losses for coastal and island communities. These are the aftereffects of COVID-19 which leads a great risk in the path of achieving the SDGs by 2030.

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